

Annual Report
2012

Contents

1. DARIAH 2012 — when everything moved off	3
2. A vision for DARIAH...	4
3. Key achievements in 2012	6
Establishing DARIAH as an EU organisation.....	6
Towards Founding Membership of DARIAH ERIC	9
DARIAH-EU in Action: the VCCs at work.....	12
Cooperation and Outreach	13
4. Coordinating DARIAH activities at the European level	16
DARIAH-EU Board of Directors	17
DARIAH-EU Coordination Office	17
Virtual Competency Centre Heads.....	17

1. DARIAH 2012 — when everything moved off

This report is small by essence. It is intended to provide the main highlights of the DARIAH-EU activities in 2012. Still, 2012 is likely to be seen as the year when DARIAH actually took off in all its infrastructural dimensions.

From an administrative point of view, the DARIAH ERIC application was submitted and successfully passed the first review leading us to the final submission stage. This success was also accompanied by a growing interest from new members to join, with very good news coming from Luxembourg, Greece, Italy and Belgium.

Beyond this political progress, the actual scientific and technical work in DARIAH has started full speed with two major VCC meetings in Utrecht and Vienna. As well as identifying concrete services above all we could see the richness and complementary nature of DARIAH contributors from all over Europe.

This dynamic is also reflected in the increase of our affiliated projects: CENDARI started, DiXiT and ARIADNE were accepted. Even more, our strong engagement in motivating communities to submit proposals to the EU consultation in October resulted in a range of strong humanities submissions which have the potential to become components of the future DARIAH network.

This series of successes gives us faith in the strategy adopted so far in relation to the various research communities DARIAH is intended to address and helps shaping our future vision in this respect.

Laurent Romary,
Director, DARIAH-EU

Laurent Romary
Director, DARIAH-EU

2. A vision for DARIAH...

An essential aspect of putting together a research infrastructure is to fulfil the expectations from its potential users. But how can we speak about expectations in general without actually keeping track of the ongoing cultural changes that occur so rapidly in the humanities at present?

DARIAH-EU in action during the General VCC meeting, Vienna

The vision we have is that the core stakeholder group for DARIAH activities are indeed research projects within the humanities that have received a national or European grant and whose work programme comprises of an important move towards using digital methods. Such projects are essential for several reasons:

- They are anchored in a clear scholarly domain, thus providing a precise insight on the underlying research issues
- They are likely to have clear needs in terms of digital data management and tools
- They have actual funding for their own grassroots developments, which are likely to bring new tools and services to the corresponding scholarly community at large
- They have a clear view that they have to take sustainability measures for their results

Digital methods in practice, German Archaeological Institute

By addressing such stakeholders, has the effect that such projects take the lead in their corresponding communities. We will therefore magnify our impact and actually, although at times indirectly, reach out a wide community of scholars in the humanities.

To do so, we need a global strategy regarding funded projects in the humanities to accompany their move to digital methods. Such a strategy should be based on the recognition of some basic services about which DARIAH Members and DARIAH-EU make a strong commitment.

As an outline, and indeed recommendation for such systematic services, we should consider:

- Disseminating information about the project, probably by offering long term hosting of their web site
- Provision of ground services needed for securing the projects' technical work
- Taking up any re-usable development or expertise to feed DARIAH VCC activities
- Offering a joint approach to making the project results sustainable
- Feeding back the projects' results to the corresponding wider communities as well as the funding agency (as best practices)

DARIAH-EU VCC Research and Education at work
Petra Links, DARIAH-NL, Costis Dallas, DARIAH-GR, Matt Munson, DARIAH-DE

Implementing such a strategy will require the combination of three complementary factors:

- Awareness of the DARIAH actors that funded projects are our main stakeholders for service provision
- Maintenance of a strong dialogue with national and European funding agencies
- Favouring the emergence of methods and training networks such as NeDiMAH and DiXiT, but also local or thematic competence networks, to facilitate the exchanges between projects and DARIAH actors.

As a final word, we would like to stress that DARIAH should play a complementary role to the actual nationally or EU funded projects whereby such projects are the place where *innovation* is carried out, whereas *consolidation* aspects are conferred to DARIAH.

3. Key achievements in 2012

Establishing DARIAH as an EU organisation

DARIAH aims to secure sustainably funding for digital arts and humanities research and education across Europe. As a step towards this goal, DARIAH is in the process of establishing itself as a European organisation or ERIC ([European Research Infrastructure Consortium](#)).

An ERIC is a specific European legal framework for research infrastructures such as DARIAH involving several countries. This is a relatively new legal framework, which formally came into force on 28 August 2009. The first ERIC to be established was the Social Science ERIC, SHARE (Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe) with The Netherlands as the Host Country on 17 March 2011. The second, CLARIN (Common Language Resources and Technology Infrastructure) on 29 February 2012, also with the Host Country of The Netherlands.

There is a formal application process for establishing an ERIC, which has been clearly defined by the European Commission, as shown in the ERIC application flowchart below.

ERIC application flowchart
[from the [ERIC Practical Guidelines](#), p10]

There are two key steps towards establishing an ERIC:

- **Step 1** – the ‘electronic application’ – this initial application is to assess compliance with the ERIC regulation
- **Step 2** - the formal request by the Host State to establish the ERIC with formal (signed) letters of commitment from Member countries.

As Members of an ERIC are countries, this is a diplomatic and political process. However this time will be well spent as it is intended that ERICs last for many years. In the case of DARIAH-ERIC an initial 20-year period, which can be renewed on agreement of the DARIAH General Assembly, is envisaged in the Statutes.

DARIAH experienced the following key challenges in establishing our ERIC:

- ERIC is a relatively new legal framework, which as of 31 December 2012, has only successfully been implemented with The Netherlands as the Host State. Each country that wishes to host an ERIC needs to develop internal procedures for enabling this at a scientific, legal and financial level. Even though ERIC is formally recognised by all EU Members States, implementing the ERIC regulation within an existing legal system is a complex process and sometimes requires amendments of existing laws.
- In order to host an ERIC, the Host Country needs the agreement of several ministries, such as the Ministry of Research (scientific content), the Ministry of Finance (related to tax exemptions that ERICs can benefit from) and sometimes the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (as an ERIC will be an international organisation). In some countries, the agreement of the government at a parliamentary level is also required. Despite the best efforts of all people concerned, liaison between ministries and cross-ministerial decision-making is a time-consuming process.
- In the case of France, which will be the Host Country for the DARIAH ERIC, the agreement of the Ministry of Higher Education and Research (scientific content), the Ministry of Finance, the Ministry of Culture and Communication and the Ministry of Foreign Affairs are required. Before obtaining this agreement, a special committee dedicated to research infrastructures (Comité directeur des très grandes infrastructures de recherche) must validate the ‘project’.
- Governments change and elections within a country can have practical implications for the establishment of an ERIC (e.g. new liaison people, new procedures etc). With a change in government, the people working within a ministry can change.

In 2012, significant progress was made towards establishing the DARIAH ERIC:

DARIAH-EU presentation for the ERIC Committee - Jacques Dubucs (French Ministry of Higher Education and Research, France) and Sally Chambers (DARIAH-EU) presented DARIAH to the ERIC Committee at the European Commission, Brussels in January 2012. The ERIC Committee will assist the European Commission in evaluating the DARIAH-ERIC application.

Inter-ministerial evaluation of DARIAH by future Host Country, France – As the future Host Country of the DARIAH ERIC, the authorities in France needed to undertake an inter-ministerial evaluation of the DARIAH documentation to check for both scientific rigour as well as legal-readiness. The Host Country Coordinator together with the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office prepared the ‘evaluation package’ for the French Ministries which included the DARIAH documents (Statutes, Technical and Scientific Description, and Business plan with a covering note in French). This evaluation package was delivered to the French Ministry of Higher Education in February 2012.

Initial results from the French inter-ministerial evaluation received – In March 2012, the initial results from the French inter-ministerial evaluation were received. Although France was happy with the scientific content of DARIAH, it became clear that further work would be needed to implement the ERIC regulation with the French legal system.

VAT Exemption Article agreed – the wording of the VAT exemption article in the draft DARIAH-ERIC statutes was agreed in June 2012. The ministerial legal experts in France, Germany and The Netherlands were instrumental in this process.

French ‘Green Light’ for DARIAH – Within the support of ERIC experts from the European Commission a solution to remove the legal obstacles related to the implementation of the ERIC framework in France has been found. The French Ministry of Higher Education has therefore convened a meeting of the French ERIC projects (DARIAH, Euro-Argo and ECRIN) in mid-June to review the next steps in the ERIC process.

Host Country approved documents circulated to DARIAH future Founding Members – Jacques Dubucs (French Ministry of Higher Education and Research, France) circulated a revised version of the draft DARIAH-ERIC Statutes incorporating the proposals made by France in liaison with the European Commission to the future DARIAH ERIC Founding Members in July for review. This version of the Statutes agreed by France, Germany and The Netherlands includes the agreed wording of the VAT exemption article.

DARIAH-ERIC Step 1 Application Submitted – In October 2012, France as the future Host Country of the DARIAH ERIC formally submitted the DARIAH ERIC Step 1 application to the European Commission. The application document will be reviewed by a group of 4-5 independent experts appointed to assist the European Commission in assessing whether the Technical and Scientific Description and the DARIAH ERIC Statutes are compliant with the ERIC regulation.

Towards the DARIAH ERIC Step 2 application

The results of the ‘Step 1’ evaluation, including details of any modifications to the documents that are required, are expected in early January 2013. A working group from the Board of Directors and the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office (DCO) has already been established to support the further submission process and undertake any revisions to the documentation should they be required by the Commission. The following steps provide an overview of the milestones leading to the DARIAH ERIC Step 2 application:

- **Amendments to DARIAH-ERIC application documents required by the European Commission**
- **Feedback on revised DARIAH-ERIC documents from future Founding Members**
- **Formal letters of commitment from countries wishing to become Founding Members of DARIAH-ERIC**

At this stage, DARIAH will be invited to submit the 'Step 2 application'. This is the formal request by France as the future Host State, to establish the DARIAH ERIC. The letters of commitment from the Member States wishing to become Founding Members of the DARIAH ERIC will be appended to the DARIAH ERIC Step 2 application. It is anticipated that the DARIAH ERIC will be established in mid to late 2013.

Towards Founding Membership of DARIAH ERIC

Members of DARIAH ERIC will be countries in the European Union and Associated States, who commit to jointly develop DARIAH. The initial standard membership period is 5 years. However, the vision, as stated in the statutes, is that DARIAH will run for 20 years, if not more. As an integrating activity DARIAH brings together the state-of-the-art digital arts and humanities activities of its member countries.

As the cash contributions for DARIAH membership come from national research budgets, it is important for countries to see how DARIAH could benefit research and researchers in their own countries.

Key benefits of participation in DARIAH could include:

- Increased **visibility** of national research at the European level
- Increased international **collaboration** opportunities; enhancing exchange of knowledge, skills, expertise, training opportunities and good practice
- Increased potential for the **sustainability** of the outcomes digital research projects after the end of project funding, helping to ensure the sustainability of tools and services
- Increased **access** to research data, tools and services via the DARIAH infrastructure
- Increased **influence** at the European and international level and increased opportunities for funding

During the preparatory phase project, *Preparing DARIAH* a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) was designed for countries to formally express their willingness to support the establishment of DARIAH as a European organisation, the DARIAH ERIC.

In November 2012, we were delighted to receive the signed Memorandum of Understanding from Luxembourg following the approval of their Government Council.

DARIAH-LU activities will be coordinated by the Centre Virtuel de la Connaissance sur l'Europe, CVCE (<http://www.cvce.eu/>).

With Luxembourg, a total of 11 countries (Austria, Croatia, Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, Luxembourg, The Netherlands, Slovenia and Serbia) have signed the DARIAH MoU.

Towards the end of 2012 discussions with the Italian National Research Council, CNR (<http://www.cnr.it>) were progressing well. It is hoped that Italy will formally sign the DARIAH MoU in early 2013. This would bring the total potential DARIAH Founding Members to 12 countries.

- Austria
- Croatia
- Denmark
- France (Host Country)
- Germany
- Greece
- Ireland
- Luxembourg
- The Netherlands
- Slovenia
- Serbia

Countries that have signed the DARIAH Memorandum of Understanding by December 2012

Each DARIAH Member will appoint a National Coordinating Institution and a National Coordinator for the coordination of national DARIAH activities and preparation of in-kind contributions. Here is a preliminary list for the countries that have signed the DARIAH MoU:

Austria

National Coordinating Institution: [Austrian Academy of Sciences](#)
 National Coordinator: [Prof. Dr. Gerhard Budin](#)

Croatia

National Coordinating Institution: [Ruđer Bošković Institute](#)
 National Coordinator: [Prof. Dr. Karolj Skala](#)

Denmark

National Coordinating Institution: [Aarhus University](#)
 National Coordinator: [Dr. Erik Champion](#)

France

National Coordinating Institution: [Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, TGE-Adonis](#)
 National Coordinator: [Dr. Sophie David](#)

Germany

National Coordinating Institution: [Göttingen State and University Library](#)
 National Coordinator: [Dr. Heike Neuroth](#)

Greece

National Coordinating Institution: [Academy of Athens](#)
 National Coordinator: [Dr. Helen Katsiadakis](#)

Italy

National Coordinating Institution: [Italian National Research Council](#)
 National Coordinator: [Dr. Luca Pezzati](#)

Ireland

National Coordinating Institution: [Trinity College Dublin](#)

National Coordinator: [Dr. Susan Schreibman](#)

Luxembourg

National Coordinating Institution: [Centre Virtuel de la Connaissance sur l'Europe](#)

National Coordinator: [Marianne Backes](#)

The Netherlands

National Coordinating Institution: [Data Archiving Networked Services](#)

National Coordinator: [Dr. Peter Doorn](#)

Serbia

National Coordinating Institution: [Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development](#)

National Coordinator: [Toma Tasovac](#)

Slovenia

National Coordinating Institution: [Institute of Contemporary History](#)

National Coordinator: [Dr. Jurij Hadalin](#)

Coordinating DARIAH Member Countries

A critical task for 2013 is to ensure that the countries that have signed the DARIAH MoU commit to become Founding Members of the DARIAH-ERIC. The National Coordinators have a key role to play here. To support the National Coordinators in this role, a **'Preparing for the Coordination Board'** meeting took place during the 2nd DARIAH General Virtual Competency Centre (VCC) meeting, on 30 November 2013, in Vienna. A key aim of the meeting was to prepare National Coordinators for their crucial role in liaising with their National Ministries for signing the letters of Commitment for the 'Step 2' DARIAH ERIC Application. The meeting, which was chaired by the DARIAH-EU Board of Directors, was attended by 13 participants from 10 countries as well as participants from the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office.

Widening Participation

DARIAH aims to enhance and support digitally-enabled research and teaching across the humanities and arts in Europe. The ongoing growth of DARIAH Member countries is a vital element in this strategic direction. Throughout 2012, the Board of Directors together with the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office and the Virtual Competency Centre Advocacy, Impact and Outreach have been liaising with countries and organisations that are interesting in participating in DARIAH. Belgium, Italy and the United Kingdom, as well as institutions such as the Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences and Vilnius University, Lithuania have expressed their interest in participating in DARIAH.

DARIAH-EU in Action: the VCCs at work.

Henk Harmsen
VCC Chief Integration Officer

DARIAH's scientific and technical activities are coordinated through a European-wide network of Virtual Competency Centres (VCCs). Each VCC is centred on a specific area of expertise:

- **VCC e-Infrastructure** will establish a shared technology platform for Arts and Humanities research
- **VCC Research and Education Liaison** will expose and share researcher's knowledge, methodologies and expertise
- **VCC Scholarly Content Management** will facilitate the exposure and sharing of scholarly content
- **VCC Advocacy, Impact and Outreach** will interface with key influencers in and for the Arts and Humanities

To complement the 'virtual' nature of DARIAH's VCC activities, General VCC meetings provide the opportunity for people working in the VCC's to meet face-to-face to work on VCC and cross-VCC activities.

In April 2012, the first General VCC meeting was held in Utrecht, The Netherlands. It was attended by over 75 participants from 15 countries.

A key aspect of this meeting was a whistle-stop tour through Europe hearing about the 'Top 3' DARIAH national activities in Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Ireland, The Netherlands, Lithuania, Serbia, Slovenia and the UK.

Heike Neuroth, DARIAH-DE, presenting DARIAH activities in Germany during the General VCC meeting, Utrecht

Laurent Romary and Tobias Blanke facilitating the 'So what is DARIAH-EU?' workshop at the General VCC meeting, Vienna

DARIAH-Austria hosted the second VCC meeting in Vienna. This meeting was attended by 80 people from 12 countries.

Recognising the value of cross-VCC collaboration was an important outcome of the Vienna meeting.

Concrete examples of cross-VCC collaboration include the development of a Persistent Identifier expert group and a task force for publication workflow processes. Showcasing DARIAH activities was an important goal for all VCCs.

Cooperation and Outreach

Building on the work in the VCCs, DARIAH will provide the necessary infrastructure to support European research programmes and projects in Arts and Humanities. **DARIAH Affiliated projects** are initiatives whose activity and even existence are closely dependent on the technical and political background established by DARIAH.

In 2012, two key European Research initiatives CENDARI and DASISH were launched and our collaboration with existing initiatives such as EHRI and NeDiMAH was strengthened. In addition, successful project proposals for ARIADNE (Advanced Research Infrastructure for Archaeological Dataset Networking in Europe) and DiXiT (Digital Scholarly Editions Initial Training Network) successfully reached the negotiation stage.

CENDARI (Collaborative European Digital/Archival Infrastructure)

The European CENDARI project (<http://www.cendari.eu/>) has been designed from the onset as a DARIAH supported project. Based on the idea of defining a virtual research environment allowing historians to identify, combine and use materials available within a network of archives across Europe, it is organised so as to facilitate the emergence of stable editorial and technical solutions. Even if the project itself has a focus on medieval and First World War materials, it is expected that most of the developed components could be easily reused by other archive-based historical research. The CENDARI Kick-off meeting took place in Brussels on 21-22 March 2012.

European Holocaust Research Infrastructure (EHRI)

In October 2010, the European Holocaust Research Infrastructure, EHRI (<http://www.ehri-project.eu/>) was launched. EHRI aims to support the European Holocaust research community by initiating new levels of collaborative research through the development of innovative methodologies and transnational access to research infrastructures and services. The DARIAH expertise has been key for planning and organising the technical service work for EHRI, in particular the research requirements, data integration and virtual research environment. DARIAH's involvement in these key development fields will ensure that access to integrated archival material will follow best practices and European standards.

DARIAH offers to EHRI its expertise in ensuring data quality and access to its registry services. In detail, DARIAH will collaborate with the following EHRI services:

- Interoperability Service such as registries for collections and metadata to support the core tasks of research data integration
- Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure to provide single-sign-on for sensitive Holocaust research data
- Persistent identifiers to identify redundant/duplicate research collections on the web.

Network for Digital Methods in the Arts and Humanities (NeDiMAH)

The ESF-funded NeDiMAH (Network for Digital Methods in the Arts and Humanities) Network (<http://www.nedimah.eu/>) is based on the assumption that there is a critical mass of digital content in the Arts and Humanities, and that researchers need to collaborate on creating awareness and understanding of how ICT-based tools and methods can make that digital content valuable for transformative research. The Network works in close collaboration with DARIAH to identify ways that researchers can use digital collections and content for research through the exploitation of digital research methods and tools. It will offer DARIAH researchers a platform to evaluate the value of digital research. All three chairs of NeDiMAH are closely involved with DARIAH and two lead on DARIAH VCC2 work nationally and European-wide.

DASISH (Data Service Infrastructure for the Social Science and Humanities)

The kick-off meeting for the EU project DASISH (<http://dasish.eu/>) took place at the Swedish National Data Service in Gothenburg on 17-19 January 2012. The project brings together all 5 ESFRI research infrastructure initiatives in the social sciences and humanities represented by: CLARIN, DARIAH, CESSDA, ESS, SHARE. The goal is to determine areas of possible synergies in infrastructure development and to work on concrete joint activities.

Here is a selection of the presentations given by the DARIAH-EU team in 2012:

Dubucs, J. and Chambers, S. **Introducing DARIAH**, ERIC Committee, European Commission, Brussels, 20 January 2012

Romary, L. **DARIAH-EU: an overview**, Joint DARIAH-AT/CLARIN-AT Meeting, Vienna, Austria, 21-22 February 2012.

Romary, L. and Chambers, S. **From Arbeitspakete to Virtual Competency Centres: participating in the DARIAH-EU conversation**, DARIAH-DE Consortium Meeting, Cologne, Germany 5-6 March 2012.

Blanke, T. and Anderson, S. **The (digital) Future of Academic publishing? Digital Research Infrastructures for the Humanities: The DARIAH Project**, London Book Fair, London, 17 April 2012.

Chambers, S. **Welcoming DIGHUMLAB and DARIAH-DK to Europe...**, DIGHUMLAB launch, Aarhus, Denmark, 10 September 2012.

Blanke, T. **The Digital Research Infrastructure for the Arts and Humanities (DARIAH): Background and achievements to date**. DARIAH-DE Scientific Advisory Board, Göttingen, 14 September 2012.

Hughes, L., Blanke, T. and Chambers, S. **Introducing DARIAH** presentation at the Arts and Humanities Research Council, Swindon, UK, 5 November 2012.

DIGHUMLAB

Denmark's first digital humanities laboratory, DIGHUMLAB, invites researchers from a large spectrum of Digital Humanists to participate in DH processes: they could be literature scholars, librarians, cartographers, game designers, linguists, journalists and archaeologists. Humanities-based disciplines and are greatly affected by the rapid growth and change of tools, methods and audiences.

DIGHUMLAB

There are currently three major research themes, these are: [Language-based materials and tools](#), [Media tools](#), and [Interaction and Design studies](#).

DIGHUMLAB aims to enhance research within communication and media studies by developing

A screenshot from the new DARIAH-EU website

The **DARIAH-EU website** (<http://dariah.eu/>) is a core communications channel for DARIAH-EU activities. Until DARIAH-EU is established as a European organisation, a DARIAH-EU transitional website has been regularly maintained, particularly with news items both from DARIAH-EU and its wider network of partners. On average at least 1 - 2 news item per week is posted to the DARIAH-EU website. A total of just under 100 news items were posted during 2012. In 2012 there were a total number of almost 22,000 users visiting the DARIAH-EU website, with an average number of visitors per month of 1,800. The most popular news item in 2012, was [TEI and the C\(r\)i\(o\)\(w\)u\)d, deadline for submissions extended](#) which was downloaded over 8000 times.

With the availability of technical support from July 2012, the development of the new DARIAH-EU website has been able to move more quickly. The goal of the new DARIAH-EU website is to become a connected network of tools, information, people and methodologies for investigating, exploring and supporting research across the broad spectrum of the Digital Humanities. The aim of the website is to become a first choice for scholars, researchers and institutions looking for information on digital arts and humanities in Europe. The content of the website is being totally redesigned, with a view to providing a much more researcher-focused website.

Key components of the website include a directory listing the contributions of DARIAH-EU Member Countries, a section detailing the goals and tasks of the Virtual Competency Centres (VCCs) as well as the organisational aspects of DARIAH-EU. Technically innovative features include a DARIAH-EU twitter wall, a high-performance search engine and in collaboration with DARIAH colleagues from Cléo (Centre pour l'édition électronique ouverte) in France, a digital humanities feed from the Social Sciences and Humanities event service, Calenda (<http://calenda.org/>). A first 'demo version' of the DARIAH-EU website was developed in time for the General VCC meeting in Vienna in November 2012. A 'soft-launch' version will be available in late Spring 2013.

In August 2012, the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office took its first steps in using social media for communication activities. By December 2012, DARIAH-EU already had 154 followers. Join us by following [@DARIAHeu](https://twitter.com/DARIAHeu).

4. Coordinating DARIAH activities at the European level

In January 2012 DARIAH-EU decided to function as far as possible as the European organisation it will become. Until the DARIAH ERIC is established a transitional DARIAH-EU Board of Directors has been put in place. The members are:

- **Dr. Laurent Romary**, Director of Research at INRIA, a French national science and technology institute dedicated to computational sciences and Guest Researcher at the Humboldt University Berlin
- **Dr. Tobias Blanke**, Senior Lecturer, Centre for e-Research, Kings' College London.
- **Dr. Conny Kristel**, Senior Researcher at the Dutch Institute for War, Holocaust and Genocide Studies (NIOD) and Project Director of the European Holocaust Research Infrastructure (EHRI).

The DARIAH-EU Board of Directors is supported by the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office (DCO). The DCO is a virtual distributed team which is responsible for the coordination of DARIAH activities at the European Level. The DARIAH-EU Coordination office (DCO) is based in three countries:

- **France:** financial and legal coordination
- **Germany:** overall coordination and communication
- **The Netherlands:** Virtual Competency Centres (VCCs) coordination.

The DARIAH-EU Coordination Office (DCO) in Göttingen is funded by the national DARIAH project in Germany, DARIAH-DE (<http://de.dariah.eu/>) and is hosted by the [Göttingen Centre for Digital Humanities](#) (GCDH).

GCDH GCDH is the cross-faculty institution of the Georg-August-Universität Göttingen that coordinates, carries out, and further develops research, teaching and infrastructure activities at the Göttingen Research Campus in the field of Digital Humanities.

The DARIAH-EU Coordination Office based in the GCDH has the following members of staff:

- **Gabriele Kraft, DARIAH-EU Communications Officer**, who is responsible for internal (e.g. Internal newsletter, mailing lists, DARIAH-EU wiki) and external communication (DARIAH-EU website, DARIAH-EU Twitter account, leaflets, information brochure and promotional materials).
- **Sally Chambers, Secretary-General of the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office**, plays a central coordination role for DARIAH at the European Level. Currently her key task is to establish DARIAH as a European organisation (DARIAH-ERIC) where she works closely with Sophie David, who coordinates DARIAH activities in France.
- **Kristine Voigt, Technical Support Officer**, supporting the technical development of the DARIAH-EU website.

DARIAH-EU Board of Directors

Laurent Romary
Director

Tobias Blanke
Director

Conny Kristel
Director

DARIAH-EU Coordination Office

Sophie David
Host Country
Coordinator

Henk Harmsen
Chief Integration
Officer

Sally Chambers
Secretary General

Gabriele Kraft
Communications
Officer

Kristine Voigt
Technical Support
Officer

Virtual Competency Centre Heads

e-Infrastructure

Karlheinz Mörth

Research and Education

Susan Schreibman

Scholarly Content Management

Sophie David

Advocacy, Impact and Outreach

**Heike Neuroth /
Dirk Wintergrün**

**Ye Cao /
René Smolarski**

Erik Champion

Laurents Sesink